

Walnut Creek Project, Franklin County (39.83290, -82.89184)

Since construction in 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Walnut Creek Project has been filtration of inflows from Walnut Creek. This Project received a large volume of nutrient-laden water in 2024. However, due to its relatively high elevation inflow notch, the volumes treated were still less than had the notch been slightly lower, as water can only inflow from the creek during extreme high flow events where large quantities of water may overload the ability of the system to remove nutrients. In 2024, the Project filtered 28 lbs phosphorus per acre. The Project also contributes 0.6 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (17.4 acres restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland consisting of a permanently flooded deep settling pool at the inflow and at the outflow, with seasonally flooded hummocks and hollows connecting the settling pools. Water enters the Project from Walnut Creek via the inflow notch at the north of the Project and exits back to Walnut Creek via the water level control structure (WLCS) at the south. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which Walnut Creek floods the wetland, possible at discharge of $\geq 1,064$ cubic feet per second.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The stop logs in the WLCS could be adjusted to retain more water inside the wetland during flow events. Increasing the stop log height by just one 18-cm stop log would promote greater residence times and water volume inside the wetland, resulting in more opportunity for nutrient filtration.
- Lowering the inflow notch would allow for more high nutrient concentration summer flows to be received by the Project, potentially supporting greater nutrient filtration. However, this may cause concern with volume capacity of the site where the whole Project would become inundated. A balance would have to be found between capturing more events and not inundating the entire Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.